

CRYSTALLINE COMPONENTS OF THE BARK OF *PRUNUS PUDDUM* (ROXB),
PART II. ON THE CONSTITUTION OF PRUNUSETIN

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A compound, m.p. 237-38°, has been isolated in 0.08 per cent yield from the ethereal extract of the bark of *Prunus puddum*. It has been named *Prunusetin* and has been shown to be 5-methoxy-7:4-dihydroxy-isoflavone. On demethylation with hydriodic acid it yields a trihydroxy compound identical with the natural isoflavone genistein.

In Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 171) of this series of investigations puddumetin isolated from the bark of *Prunus puddum*, has been shown to be 7-methoxy-5:4'-dihydroxyflavone identical with genkwanin isolated by Nakao and Tseng (*J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1932, No. 602, 343; 1933, No. 608, 905) from a Chinese drug 'Yuen-Hua.'

This paper deals with the constitution of the second compound, which has been named *prunusetin*. It crystallises from ethyl acetate and glacial acetic acid as pale yellow shining needles, m.p. 237-38°.

Analytical data of prunusetin are in agreement with the formula $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ and hence it is isomeric with puddumetin. It is soluble in caustic alkali with a permanent deep yellow colour. Ferric chloride imparts a brown-violet coloration showing the presence of phenolic-OH group. It contains two OH groups as it easily forms a colorless diaetyl derivative, m.p. 220-22°. Methoxyl estimation by Zeisel's method indicates the presence of one OMe group and hence prunusetin may be written as $C_{15}H_{10}O_5(OMe)(OH)_2$.

Prunusetin is insoluble in alkali carbonate and bicarbonate. From the yellow alkaline solution the original substance is recovered on acidification. These properties and the molecular formula of the compound suggest a chromone structure for prunusetin, namely (I).

Prunusetin remains unaffected when air is aspirated through its alkaline solution for three hours. On methylation with methyl iodide it produces a dimethyl ether, m.p. 160-61°, which is insoluble in alkali and cannot be further acetylated. When prunusetin is demethylated with hydriodic acid for one hour in an atmosphere of dry carbon dioxide, a trihydroxy compound, m.p. 291-93°, is isolated which is found to be identical in all respects with the natural isoflavone genistein (II) (Perkin and Newbery, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 830; Perkin and Horsfall, *ibid.* 1900, 77, 1340; Baker and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1928, 3115), the coloring matter of Dyer's Broom. The derivatives of the demethylated product are identical with those of genistein described in the literature (Baker and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1981).

TABLE I

Demethylated product of prunusetin. m.p. 291-93°	Genistein, m.p. 291-93° (synthetic).	Mixed m.p. 292-93° 201
Triacetyl derivative	197-201°	
Dimethyl ether	137-39°	
Acetylated dimethyl ether	202-204°	
<i>O</i> -methylated dimethyl ether	200-201.5°	
Trimethyl ether	160-62°	161°

Prunusetin is thus a monomethoxy derivative of genistein and is isomeric with the natural isoflavone, prunetin (III) or (IV) (Finnemore, *Pharm. J.*, 1910, 81, 604; Baker and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1022) isolated from *Prunus serotina*. It is not, however, identical with prunetin as shown below.

TABLE II

	Prunetin, m.p. 242° m.p. 224-26° 145°	Prunusetin, m.p. 237-39° 220-22° No monomethyl derivative is formed m.p. 160-61°
Diacetyl derivative		
Monomethyl ether (which forms an acetyl derivative)		
Dimethyl ether (which does not form an acetyl derivative)	The formation of dimethyl ether is not recorded in literature	

Since Prunusetin readily forms a dimethyl ether, which does not contain a free hydroxyl group, it seems likely that it has a methoxyl group in position 5 and its probable constitution is (V) though according to Bose and Nath (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 141; cf. Shah, Virkar, Venkataraman, *ibid.*, 1942, 19, 135) a benzopyrone with a methoxyl group in position 5 does not usually occur in nature.

For want of sufficient material, prunusetin could not be hydrolysed in quantity, but in a trial experiment a ketone, forming a semicarbazone, was obtained in traces. Experiments towards the synthesis of prunusetin in support of the structure (V) are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

The powdered bark (600 g.) was extracted with ether (16 hours). The brown ethereal extract was concentrated to about one-tenth of its volume and kept overnight. The yellow solid which separated out was filtered and the filtrate was freed from the solvent. A brown oil was obtained which solidified on keeping to a gelatinous mass.

Isolation of Prunusetin.—The yellow solid obtained above was a mixture of two substances, one being less soluble in alcohol than the other, crystallised first from alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. above 270°. The more soluble fractions crystallised from alcohol as light yellow needles, m.p. 224-30°. The latter on repeated crystallisation from glacial acetic acid melted at 237-38° (A). Variation of solvent such as ethyl acetate, nitrobenzene did not raise the melting point. From acetic acid mother-liquor was obtained a pale yellow solid, m.p. 224-26° (B).

The gelatinous mass obtained above was treated in a similar manner as described in Part I (Chakravarti and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*). Light brown crystals, m.p. 224-30°, were obtained. These together with the fraction (B), obtained above, were just dissolved in boiling ethyl acetate and allowed to stand overnight. First two or three crops of crystals had the melting point above 270°. The ethyl acetate mother-liquor on evaporation gave a solid which crystallised from glacial acetic acid as pale yellow shining needles, m.p. 237-38°, identical with the product (A), the total yield being 0.06% of the weight of the dry bark.

Prunusetin (5-methoxy-7 : 4'-dihydroxyisoflavone) is soluble in alcohol, ethyl acetate, sparingly soluble in ether, benzene, and insoluble in chloroform. It is readily soluble in cold caustic alkali solutions with yellow colour, but it is insoluble in alkali carbonate and bicarbonate. An alcoholic solution of the substance gives the brown-violet coloration with ferric chloride. It produces no coloration when its alcoholic solution is reduced with magnesium and hydrochloric acid in the cold. [Found in a sample dried over P₂O₅ in vacuum at 110-15° : C, 67.56 ; H, 4.02 ; OMe, 10.87. C₁₅H₁₀O₄(OMe) requires C, 67.61 ; H, 4.22 ; OMe, 10.92 per cent].

Diacetylprunusetin (5-methoxy-7 : 4'-diacetoxyisoflavone) was obtained by gently refluxing prunusetin with acetic anhydride and two drops of dry pyridine. After one hour the mixture was cooled, diluted with water, heated on a boiling water-bath for a few minutes and allowed to stand. The white solid was collected, washed with water and crystallised from rectified spirit as white shining plates, m.p. 220-22°. [Found in a sample dried over P₂O₅ at 110-15° in vacuum : C, 65.33. H, 4.65 ; C₁₇H₁₄O₆(OMe) requires C, 65.21 ; H, 4.31 per cent].

Prunusetin dimethyl ether (7 : 5 : 4'-trimethoxyisoflavone) was prepared by refluxing for 2 hours a solution of prunusetin (0.1 g.) in dry acetone with methyl iodide (10 c.c.) in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.). The mixture was filtered, the filtrate evaporated to dryness, and the residue crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless needles

m.p. 160-61°. It is found to be identical with genistein trimethyl ether (mixed m.p.). [Found in a sample dried over P_2O_5 at 100° in vacuum : C, 69.00; H, 5.05; OMe, 28.78. $C_{15}H_{10}O_5(OMe)_3$, requires C, 69.23; H, 5.12; OMe, 29.81 per cent].

Attempted Acetylation of Prunusetin Dimethyl ether.—The above dimethyl ether was refluxed with acetic anhydride and pyridine in the usual manner. The solid crystallised from rectified spirit as colourless needles, m.p. 160-61° (mixed m.p. with prunusetin dimethyl ether 160-61°).

Attempted aerial oxidation of Prunusetin.—Air was aspirated through an aqueous caustic potash solution of prunusetin for 3 hours and the solution was kept overnight. On acidification the solid was collected and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as pale yellow needles, m.p. 237-38° (mixed m.p. with prunusetin 237-38°).

Demethylation of Prunusetin with Hydriodic acid : Isolation of Genistein.—Prunusetin (0.1 g.) was heated for 1 hour at 130-35° in a glycerine bath with hydriodic acid (sp. gr. 1.7, 10 c.c.) in an atmosphere of dry carbon dioxide. The mixture was cooled and diluted with water. The separated solid was filtered, washed with sodium thiosulphate solution, then with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol as colorless shining needles, m.p. 291-93° (and mixed m.p. with synthetic genistein). (Found in a sample dried over P_2O_5 at 115-20° in vacuum : C, 66.63; H, 4.04. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{10}O_5$: C, 66.67; H, 3.7 per cent).

Triacetylgenistein.—The demethylated product (0.1 g.) was acetylated in the usual manner. The product crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless shining flakes, m.p. 202-203°. [Found in a sample dried over P_2O_5 at 105-10° in vacuum : C, 63.60; H, 4.15. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{14}O_8(COCH_3)_3$: C, 63.63; H, 4.04 per cent].

C-methylated genistein dimethyl ether (6-methyl-7 : 4'-dimethoxygenistein) was obtained by refluxing for 3 hours a solution of the demethylated product in dry acetone with methyl iodide and anhydrous potassium carbonate in the usual manner. The reaction mixture was freed from the solvent and the residue crystallised from dilute alcohol as silky needles, m.p. 201-202°.

Genistein Dimethylether (7 : 4'-dimethoxy-genistein).—An ice-cooled solution of the demethylated product (0.1 g.) in absolute alcohol (Ca-dried) was treated with a cold ethereal solution of diazomethane (3 mol.) in dry ether and the mixture was kept overnight. Ether was removed, the mixture neutralised with acetic acid and diluted with water. The solid separating was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol as colorless shining needles, m.p. 139-40°. (Found in a sample dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum at 90-95° : C, 68.10; H, 4.80. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$: C, 68.45; H, 4.73 per cent).

Acetylgenistein dimethyl ether (5-acetoxy-7 : 4'-dimethoxyisoflavone).—The above dimethyl ether was acetylated with acetic anhydride and pyridine in the usual manner. The product crystallised from dilute alcohol as shining plates, m.p. 202-204°.

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